

OVERCOMING WORKPLACE BURNOUT AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON JOB SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR STRESS MANAGEMENT ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational research was conducted to assess the relationship between the level of workplace burnout and the level of job satisfaction among the faculty and staff of the West Visayas State University system during the first semester of the academic year 2025 - 2026. It further aimed to determine the most prevalent causes of workplace burnout and the most common coping mechanisms employed by the respondents in dealing with workplace burnout. The influence of the respondents' perception on their workplace climate was considered in the investigation. A total of 151 employees (faculty and staff) from the various campuses of the University were invited to participate in the study. The campuses where the investigation was conducted were identified through cluster sampling and the draw-lots method. The respondents themselves were identified through convenience sampling. The respondents were subsequently classified according to socio-demographic characteristics and according to their perceptions of their workplace climate. A researcher-made questionnaire designed to elicit data on the respondents' personal profile, the most prevalent causes of workplace burnout among them, the coping mechanisms they employed to mitigate burnout, the level (intensity) of workplace burnout they experienced, their assessment of their workplace climate, and their level of job satisfaction was used as data gathering instrument. The different questionnaires comprising the instrument were subjected to reliability and validity testing. The mean, the ranking, Kruskal-Wallis Test, the Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test, and Spearman's rho were used as basis in analyzing and interpreting the data. The data were processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), with the level of significance set at 0.05. The results revealed that the three most prevalent causes of workplace burnout

among them was 'unrealistic' deadlines in the submission of outputs/accomplishments, the frequency of changes in how their work was done and the format of the documents used which they believed kept them from becoming proficient in their jobs, and the extra assignments (accreditation, ISO, etc.) they were given aside from their regular workload. Meanwhile, the three most common methods used by the respondents in coping with workplace burnout was praying, spending quality time with their families and loved ones, and continuing to update themselves with new knowledge and skills relevant to their jobs to make their work easier. The findings further revealed that, as an entire group, as well as those respondents who perceived their workplace climates to be 'excellent', experienced 'low' levels of workplace burnout; while those who perceived their workplace climates to be 'poor', 'satisfactory', or 'very satisfactory' experienced 'moderate' levels of workplace burnout. Moreover, findings showed that, as an entire group, as well as those respondents who perceived their workplace climate to be 'satisfactory' or 'very satisfactory' had 'high' levels of job satisfaction; on the other hand, those who perceived their workplace climate to be 'poor' had a 'low' level of job satisfaction, while those who perceived their workplace climate to be 'excellent' had a 'very high' level of job satisfaction. The research also revealed the following: there were significant differences in the levels of workplace burnout among the respondents in the various categories of their perceptions of their workplace climates; there were highly significant differences in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents in the various categories of their perceptions of their workplace climates; and there was a negative and highly significant correlation between the respondents' of workplace burnout and their level of job satisfaction. The study concluded that the respondents' workplace burnout was a significant and valid predictor of the respondents' job satisfaction; that is, the more favorable their perception of their workplace climate, the higher was their job satisfaction, and vice, versa.

Keywords: *Workplace Burnout, Workplace Climate, Coping Mechanisms, Job Satisfaction, WVSU Employees*

INTRODUCTION

Workplace burnout is a state of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged or excessive workplace stress. It is characterized by feelings of cynicism, negativity, and reduced professional efficacy. Essentially, it is when work-related stress becomes overwhelming and impacts a person's ability to function effectively and find satisfaction in their job (Mayo Clinic Staff, n.d.in Verampala, 2023).

Burnout develops over time due to ongoing work-related stress, rather than a single event. Burnout involves feeling physically, emotionally, and mentally drained. Individuals may develop a negative or detached attitude towards their work, colleagues, or clients.

Burnout can lead to a decrease in productivity, performance, and a sense of accomplishment. It can affect both mental and physical health, potentially leading to depression, anxiety, and other health problems.

While burnout is a serious issue, it is not currently recognized as a medical diagnosis in the same way as conditions like depression. However, burnout can overlap with and sometimes be a precursor to mental health conditions (World Health Organization - WHO, 2019 in APA, 2023).

Job satisfaction, on the other hand, is defined as the level of contentment employees feel with their job. This goes beyond their daily duties to cover satisfaction with team members/managers, satisfaction with organizational policies, and the impact of their job on employees' personal lives (Spiceworks, 2020).

Job satisfaction in the education sector is complex, influenced by various factors including work environment, school climate, leadership, and individual characteristics. Studies show that teachers' perceptions of student behavior, school disciplinary climate, and the support they receive from school leadership significantly impact their job satisfaction. Furthermore, factors like salary, opportunities for professional development, and the overall work environment play a crucial role in teacher morale and retention (META, 2025).

Several researches have linked job satisfaction with workplace burnout. The concept of burnout is described as a response to the imbalance between the demands of work and personal resources (Maslach & Leiter, 2017). A high level of job stress, heavy volume of work, lack of social support, and role ambiguity are involved significantly in the onset of burnout syndrome and it is related to negative attitudes toward patients and retire from work, absenteeism and job rotation. A person who is suffering from burnout often feels both physically and emotionally tired, unhappy with the job, has reduced efficiency, and feels alienated from colleagues. Job dissatisfaction is related to various behaviors, such as absenteeism, turnover intention, and job rotation. Job satisfaction has a major impact on job-related behaviors, such as turnover intention, absenteeism, and job performance (Vahey et al., 2004 in Kabir et al., 2016).

Job satisfaction in the education sector is a critical aspect of educational management. It directly impacts teacher, as well as support services, performance, student outcomes, and overall school effectiveness. When teachers are satisfied with their work, they are more likely to engage in effective teaching practices, foster positive relationships with students, and contribute to a healthy school climate. Conversely, low job satisfaction can lead to burnout, attrition, and diminished educational quality. In recent years, the focus on understanding and enhancing teacher job satisfaction has intensified, especially in the context of public education systems worldwide (Kabir et al., 2016).

Although there have been previous researches on burnout and job satisfaction, circumstances vary in different situations, time, and place; therefore, this researcher has deemed it worthwhile and crucial to conduct an investigation into the association between these two phenomena. As a candidate for a doctorate degree, major in Educational Management, the researcher has a profound interest in identifying factors that may affect the effectiveness and the efficiency of the workers in the workplace, especially in educational institutions – hence this study.

Research Questions

This descriptive-correlational study was conducted to determine the association between level workplace burnout and the level of job satisfaction among the faculty and the non-teaching staff of the West Visayas State University system during the academic year 2025 – 2026. It further aimed to determine the most prevalent causes of workplace burnout and the most common coping mechanisms employed by this group of respondents to deal with workplace burnout.

1. What is/are the most prevalent cause/s of workplace burnout among the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
2. What is/are the most common coping mechanism/s (strategies) employed by the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
3. What is the level of workplace burnout among the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
4. What is the level of job satisfaction among the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
5. Are there significant differences in the levels of workplace burnout among the respondents classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
6. Are there significant differences in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents classified according to their perception of their workplace climate?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the level of workplace burnout experienced by the respondents and their level of job satisfaction?

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

This study was anchored on the following theories: Mayo's Human Relations theory (Elton Mayo, 1880 -1949 in Verampala, 2023); Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Abraham Maslow, 1908 – 1970 in Hulatt & Freitas, 2022; McLeod, 2025); Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation-Hygiene (Frederick Irving Herzberg, 1923 – 2000 in Nickerson, 2025); The Job Demands- Resources (JD-R) Model (Tummers & Bakker, 2021); and the Coping Theory (Carver et al., 1989 in Chowdhury, 2021).

Job or workplace burnout is a state of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged workplace stress. It is characterized by feelings of being overwhelmed, cynical about work, and ineffective. Burnout can negatively impact various aspects of life, including work performance, relationships, and overall well-being (Cox et al., 2003 in Golembiewski et al., 2023).

In Human Resources, the concept of work climate refers to the internal environment of a company. An environment in which relationships with employees are built and which influences their behavior. And the better they perceive it or feel it to be based on the practices carried out, the better results will be achieved in the company. As with any other relationship, when employees are cared for, both in treatment and conditions, they become loyal to the organization and work harder to get things done (McKinsey, 2001 in Telefonica, n.d.).

Conversely, when the atmosphere in the office is a negative experience for staff, it takes a toll on their motivation. Although the corporate or organizational climate goes beyond the physical environment of the office, the physical environment is one of its components, along with working conditions and organizational culture; it is influenced by the values of the company, the form of leadership, whether it is a comfortable and pleasant space, recognition of achievements, personal relationships, communication, competitiveness, equality policy, fair remuneration (Adamopoulos et al., 2022; Çelik, 2018, in Lubbadah, 2020).

Most of the literature and the results of previous studies cited in this investigation agree that workplace climate impacts burnout among employees in such a way that employees who find their work climate favorable tend to have a higher level of organizational commitment which is the opposite of job burnout. On the other hand, employees who find the workplace climate unfavorable may experience a more intense level of job burnout earlier and may tend to have a lower level of organizational commitment (Gulmatico, 2022, Adamopoulos et al., 2022); Lubbadah, 2020); Xia et al., 2024; Ogresta et al., 2020; Rössler, 2012; Ahola et al., 2017).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This descriptive-correlational research was conducted to assess the relationship between the level of workplace burnout and the level of job satisfaction among the faculty and staff at selected campuses of the West Visayas State University system during the first semester of the academic year 2025 - 2026. It further aimed to determine the most prevalent causes of workplace burnout and the most common coping mechanisms employed by the respondents in dealing with workplace burnout. The influence of the respondents' perception on their workplace climate was considered in the investigation.

According to Bhandari (2023), descriptive correlational research is a quantitative research method that describes the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. This means that researchers observe and analyze how changes in one variable are associated with changes in another. The primary goal of this type of research is to understand the extent to which variables co-vary or move together without attempting to establish a cause-and-effect relationship.

The Respondents

A total of 151 employees (faculty and staff) from the various campuses of the University were invited to participate in the study. The campuses where the investigation was conducted were identified through cluster sampling and the draw-lots method. The respondents themselves were identified through convenience sampling.

The respondents were subsequently classified according to socio-demographic characteristics and according to their perceptions of their workplace climate.

Table 1 shows that, of the 151 respondents, majority (80 or 52.98%) perceived their work climate as 'excellent', 44 (29.14%) as 'very satisfactory', 23 (15.23%) as 'satisfactory', and 4 (2.65%) as 'poor'

Table 1

The Respondents' Profile

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Entire Group	151	100.00
Perception of their Organizational Climate		
Very Poor	0	0.00
Poor	4	2.65
Satisfactory	23	15.23
Very Satisfactory	44	29.14
Excellent	80	52.98
Total	151	100.00

The Research Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire designed to elicit data on the respondents' personal profile, the most prevalent causes of workplace burnout among them, the coping mechanisms they employed to mitigate burnout, the level (intensity) of workplace burnout they experienced, their assessment of their workplace climate, and their level of job satisfaction was used as data gathering instrument. The research instrument was submitted for face and content validation to a panel of experts. The questionnaires comprising the instrument were likewise pilot-tested using Cronbach's alpha. The following reliability indices were obtained: Organizational Climate – 0.973; Job Satisfaction - 0.971 20; Coping Mechanisms - 0.83; and Workplace Burnout - 0.921.

The Data Gathering Procedure

With assistance from the research adviser, the researcher conceptualized a topic for the research. The problem was then presented to the oral defense committee for approval. After the approval of the research problem, the manuscript for the pre-oral defense was prepared and the questionnaire was drafted. The research was then packaged for pre-oral defense.

After the pre-oral defense, the researcher secured permissions to conduct the study from the top management of West Visayas State University – Calinog Campus and from the different campus administrators of the campuses the researcher had identified as venues of the investigation. Formal letters were sent to the campus administrators for this purpose

After the securing the necessary approval, the researcher embarked on data gathering by distributing the questionnaire personally to the respondents. After retrieving the filled questionnaires the researcher organized, analyzed and interpreted the data using appropriate statistical tools.

Statistical Data Analysis Procedure

The mean, the ranking, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Spearman's rho were used as basis in analyzing and interpreting the data.

The Mean. This was used as basis in determining the level of workplace burnout experienced by the respondents, the perception on the workplace climate, and the level of job satisfaction among the respondents.

The following scales of the mean were used for the following purposes:

For Level of Workplace Burnout: 0.00 – 0.80 – very low; 0.81 – 1.60 – low; 1.61 – 2.40 – moderate; 2.41 – 3.20 – high; and 3.21 – 4.00 – very high.

For Level of Job Satisfaction: 0.00 – 0.80 – very low; 0.81 – 1.60 – low; 1.61 – 2.40 – moderate; 2.41 – 3.20 – high; and 3.21 – 4.00 – very high.

For Workplace Climate: 0.00 – 0.80 – very poor; 0.81 – 1.60 – poor; 1.61 – 2.40 – satisfactory; 2.41 – 3.20 – very satisfactory; and 3.21 – 4.00 – excellent.

Ranking. This was used to identify the most prevalent cause/s of workplace burnout among the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate. It was further used to identify the most common coping mechanism/s (strategies) employed by the respondents as an entire group and as classified according to their perception of their workplace climate.

Kruskal-Wallis Test. This was used to determine the significance of the differences of the levels of workplace burnout and in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents in the various categories of their perceptions of their workplace climate. The researcher used non-probability (convenience) sampling in identifying the respondents.

Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test. This was used to further analyze significant Kruskal-Wallis Test results in pair-wise comparisons. The researcher used non-probability (convenience) sampling in identifying the respondents.

Spearman's rho. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the respondents' level of workplace burnout and job satisfaction. The researcher used non-probability (convenience) sampling in identifying the respondents.

The data were processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), with the level of significance set at 0.05.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study with their corresponding discussions and interpretations. It consists of two parts: 1) Descriptive Data Analysis; and 2) Inferential Data Analysis.

Descriptive Data Analysis

Causes of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents as an Entire Group

Table 2 shows that "Unrealistic deadlines in the submission of outputs/ accomplishments pressure me" (M = 2.48; Rank – 1st; Desc. - High) was the most prevalent cause of workplace burnout among the respondents. "The frequency of

changes in how my work is done and the format of the documents used keep me from becoming proficient in my job” (M = 2.34; Rank – 2nd; Desc. - Moderate), and “The extra assignments (accreditation, ISO, etc.) I am given aside from my regular workload exhaust me” (M = 2.33; Rank – 3rd; Desc. - Moderate) followed respectively.

These results indicate that for the respondents as an entire group the main cause of the burnout they experienced in the work place was time pressure, which they described as ‘unrealistic’, with regard to the submission of reports and other documents. This is probably because they had been required to submit these documents at such a limited time that they felt was too insufficient. Moreover, the respondents also experienced heavy burden with the frequency of changes in how the work they had to do and in the frequent changes in the format of the documents (i.e. syllabus, research format, etc.) that they had to accomplish. Probably they felt that before they could develop some higher level of expertise and proficiency in these tasks, the required methods for these tasks and the format for these documents were changed again. Further, the extra assignments, especially during the accreditations, aside from their regular working loads also contribute significantly to the workplace burnout experienced by the respondents and caused them to feel overwhelmed by their workloads, and they had to work long hours and had to take their work home.

The findings of the present investigation may be explained by the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Tummers & Bakker, 2021) which points out aspects of the job that require sustained effort and are associated with physiological and psychological costs. Examples of this include workload, time pressure, and emotional demands. The framework postulates that high job demands and low job resources can lead to increased stress, burnout, and decreased motivation.

The results of this study revealed that job demands, especially concerning time pressure, adjustment to new methods and formats for documents, work load, the extra assignments during accreditation periods, etc. were the most prevalent factors which contributed to the level of workplace burnout experienced by the respondents.

Table 2

Causes of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents as an Entire Group

Statements	N	Mean	Rank	Description
1. The frequency of changes in how my work is done and the format of the documents used keep me from becoming proficient in my job.	151	2.34	2	Moderate
2. The extra assignments (accreditation, ISO, etc.) I am given aside from my regular workload exhaust me.	151	2.33	3	Moderate
3. Unrealistic deadlines in the submission of outputs/accomplishments pressure me.	151	2.48	1	High

Scale: 0.00 – 0.80 – Very Low; 0.81 – 1.60 – Low; 1.61 – 2.40 – Moderate; 2.41 – 3.20 – High
3.21 – 4.00 – Very High

The Most Common Coping Mechanisms among the Respondents as an Entire Group

Table 3 shows that “I pray because I find solace and comfort in prayer”(M = 3.50; Rank – 1st; Desc. – Frequently) was the most common method used by the respondents as an entire group in coping with workplace burnout. “I take every opportunity to spend quality time with my family and loved ones” (M = 3.42; Rank – 2nd; Desc. – Constantly), “I continue to update myself with new knowledge and skills relevant to my job to make my work easier (M = 3.32; Rank – 3rd; Desc. – Constantly), “I try to establish positive relationship with other people at work especially with my superiors despite the strain caused by the daily routine at work” (M = 3.18; Rank – 4th; Desc. – Frequently), and “I take control of my emotions whenever I feel like I’m breaking down” (M = 3.11; Rank – 5th; Desc. – Frequently) followed respectively.

These findings indicate that most of the respondents believed that through praying they would be able to overcome the burnout they encountered in their workplaces. The respondents also preferred to ease the burdens that they experienced through spending quality time with their families and divert their attention from the rigors of their jobs by continuing to develop their knowledge and skills regarding their jobs, and by establishing harmonious relationships with their colleagues. Controlling their emotions was also another way the respondents coped with workplace burnout because uncontrolled emotions was known to contribute to the feeling of burnout about something.

The findings of the present investigation are comparable to those of the study conducted by Gulmatico (2022) on the stress and coping mechanisms among court employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study (Gulmatico, 2022) suggested that the respondents mostly used distraction and emotional coping rather than active coping. Praying and trying to forget or ignoring what was really happening rather than finding means to confront the pandemic actively may have helped the respondents deal with the stress. Likewise, in the study of Park et al. (2020), majority of the respondents similarly reported greater emotion and religious support coping.

Table 3

The Most Common Coping Mechanisms among the Respondents as an Entire Group

Statements	N	Mean	Rank	Description
1. I continue to update myself with new knowledge and skills relevant to my job to make my work easier.	151	3.32	3	Constantly
2. I pray because I find solace and comfort in prayer.	151	3.50	1	Constantly
3. I take every opportunity to spend quality time with my family and loved ones.	151	3.42	2	Constantly

Scale: 0.00 – 0.80 – Rarely; 0.81 – 1.60 – Seldom; 1.61 – 2.40 – Occasionally; 2.41 – 3.20 - Frequently; and 3.21 – 4.00 – Constantly

The Level of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents

Table 4 shows that, as an entire group, the respondents experienced a 'low' level (M = 1.59) of workplace burnout. The table further shows that the respondents who perceived their workplace climates to be 'poor' (M = 2.40), 'satisfactory' (M = 1.75), or 'vary satisfactory' (M = 1.72) experienced 'moderate' levels of workplace burnout. On the other hand, those who perceived their workplace climates to be 'excellent' (M = 1.43) experienced a 'low' level of workplace burnout.

It is evident in the results that the respondents who had more favorable perceptions of their workplace climate experienced lower levels of workplace burnout. This indicates that workers who felt motivated and had sensed collaboration, efficiency, rapport and support from their colleagues and superiors in the workplace experienced less work-related chronic stress, emotional exhaustion, psychological distance or negativity, and low feelings of inefficacy.

These findings are support those of McKinsey (2001), in Telefonica, (n.d.), which pointed out that in an environment in which relationships with employees are built and which influences their behavior and the better they perceive it or feel it to be based on the practices carried out, the better results will be achieved in the company. As with any other relationship, when employees are cared for, both in treatment and conditions, they become loyal to the organization and work harder to get things done. Conversely, when the atmosphere in the office is a negative experience for staff, it takes a toll on their motivation.

Table 4

The Level of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents as an Entire Group and as Classified according to the Categories of their Perception of their Workplace Climate

Category	N	Mean	Description
Entire Group	151	1.59	Low
Perception of Workplace Climate			
Poor	4	2.40	Moderate
Satisfactory	23	1.75	Moderate
Very Satisfactory	44	1.72	Moderate
Excellent	80	1.43	Low

Scale: 0.00 – 0.80 – Very Low; 0.81 – 1.60 – Low; 1.61 – 2.40 – Moderate; 2.41 – 3.20 – High; 3.21 – 4.00 – Very High

The Level of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents

Table 5 shows that, as an entire group, the respondents had a 'high' level (M = 3.11) of job satisfaction. The table further shows that the respondents who perceived their workplace climate to be 'poor' had a 'low' level (M = 1.60) of job satisfaction, while those who perceived their workplace climate to be 'satisfactory' (M = 2.50) or 'very satisfactory' (M = 2.98) had 'high' levels of job satisfaction. On the other hand, those who perceived their workplace climate to be 'excellent' had a 'very high' level (M = 3.43) of job satisfaction.

It is evident in the findings of the present investigation that the respondents who had a more favorable perception of their workplace climate tended to have a higher level of job satisfaction, and vice versa.

These findings corroborate those Xia et al., (2024) which found a close intertwining between job satisfaction and work climate; a positive work climate is strongly associated with higher job satisfaction. A positive work climate, characterized by factors like supportive leadership, teamwork, and clear communication, fosters a sense of well-being and engagement, leading employees to feel more satisfied with their jobs. Conversely, a negative work climate, marked by poor communication, lack of support, and unhealthy competition, can significantly decrease job satisfaction and lead to stress and decreased productivity. Xia et al. (2024) added that a positive work climate, often described as healthy and safe, includes aspects like collaboration, growth opportunities, recognition, and employee involvement. These elements contribute to a sense of psychological safety, where employees feel valued and supported, leading to increased job satisfaction. On the other hand, when the work climate is negative, with factors like job inflexibility, lack of supervisory support, or poor communication, employees tend to experience lower job satisfaction and higher stress levels. This can manifest as decreased motivation, reduced engagement, and even increased turnover.

Table 5

The Level of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents as an Entire Group and as Classified according to the Categories of their Perception of their Workplace Climate

Category	N	Mean	Description
Entire Group	151	3.11	High
Perception of Workplace Climate			
Poor	4	1.60	Low
Satisfactory	23	2.50	High
Very Satisfactory	44	2.98	High
Excellent	80	3.43	Very High

Scale: 0.00 – 0.80 – Very Low; 0.81 – 1.60 – Low; 1.61 – 2.40 – Moderate; 2.41 – 3.20 – High; 3.21 – 4.00 – Very High

Inferential Data Analysis

The Differences in the Levels of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate

The Kruskal-Wallis Test result in Table 6 reveals significant differences [$\chi^2(3) = 12.663$; $p = 0.005$] in the levels of workplace burnout among the respondents in the various categories of their perceptions of their workplace climates. This indicates that their feeling of work-related chronic stress, emotional exhaustion, psychological distance or negativity, and feelings of inefficacy were significantly influenced by the respondents' feeling of well-being or lack of it in their workplace.

The null hypothesis assuming non-significant differences in the levels of workplace burnout among the respondents classified according to their perceptions of their workplace climates was rejected.

These findings somehow confirmed those of McKinsey (2001), in Telefonica, (n.d.), which pointed out that in an environment in which relationships with employees are built and which influences their behavior and the better they perceive it or feel it to be based on the practices carried out, the better results will be achieved in the company. This means that when employees ‘feel good’ about the environment in their jobs, they tend to be better motivated; thus experiencing less burnout.

Table 6

The Kruskal-Wallis Test Result for the Differences in the Levels of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	χ^2	df	p-value
Perception of Workplace Climate			12.663*	3	0.005
Poor	4	122.38			
Satisfactory	23	89.04			
Very Satisfactory	44	84.05			
Excellent	80	65.51			

*p < 0.05

The Pair-Wise Comparisons for the Differences in the Levels of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate

The Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test result in Table 7 reveals significant differences in the levels of workplace burnout between the respondents who perceived their workplace climates as ‘poor’ and those who perceived their workplace climates as ‘excellent’ (z = 2.387; p = 0.017), between those who perceived their workplace climates as ‘satisfactory’ and those who perceived their workplace climates as ‘excellent’ (z = 2.307; p = 0.021), and between those who perceived their workplace climates as ‘very satisfactory’ and those who perceived their workplace climates as ‘excellent’ (z = 2.274; p = 0.023).

No other pair-wise comparison of the means yielded a significant difference.

Table 7***The Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test Result for the Differences in the Levels of Workplace Burnout among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate***

Compared Groups	Z	p-value
Perception of Workplace Climate		
Poor vs. Satisfactory	1.778	0.075
Poor vs. Very Satisfactory	1.718	0.086
Poor vs. Excellent	2.387*	0.017
Satisfactory vs. Very Satisfactory	0.463	0.644
Satisfactory vs. Excellent	2.307*	0.021
Very Satisfactory vs. Excellent	2.274*	0.023

*p < 0.05

The Differences in the Levels of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate

The Kruskal-Wallis Test result in Table 16 reveals highly significant differences [$\chi^2(3) = 46.990$; $p = 0.000$] in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents in the various categories of their perceptions of their workplace climates. This indicates that their feeling of contentment with their job was significantly influenced by the respondents' feeling of well-being or lack of it in their workplace.

The null hypothesis assuming non-significant differences in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents classified according to their perceptions of their workplace climates was rejected.

These findings may be explained by Herzberg's two-factor theory which suggests that job satisfaction is influenced by two factors: motivators and hygiene factors.

Motivators, like recognition and achievement, lead to higher satisfaction and motivation. Hygiene factors, such as salary and working conditions, prevent dissatisfaction but do not necessarily motivate. According to Herzberg, both sets of factors are needed to create a productive work environment (Nickerson, 2025).

Considering that the findings indicated that the respondents who had more favorable perceptions of their workplace environment had significantly higher levels of job satisfaction may point out to the fact that these respondents may have experienced both motivators, i.e. recognition and achievement, and hygiene factors such as sufficient salary and favorable workplace conditions which caused them to have higher levels of job satisfaction.

Further, the findings also somehow confirmed those of McKinsey (2001), in Telefonica, (n.d.) which averred that when employees 'feel good' about the environment in their jobs, they tend to be better motivated; thus experiencing less burnout and higher level of job satisfaction.

Table 8***The Kruskal-Wallis Test Result for the Differences in the Levels of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate***

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	χ^2	df	p-value
Perception of Workplace Climate			46.990***	3	0.000
Poor	4	18.13			
Satisfactory	23	39.30			
Very Satisfactory	44	61.69			
Excellent	80	97.31			

***p < 0.000

The Pair-Wise Comparisons for the Differences in the Levels of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate

The Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test result in Table 9 reveals significant differences in the levels of job satisfaction between the respondents who perceived their workplace climates as 'poor' and those who perceived their workplace climates as 'very satisfactory' ($z = 2.336$; $p = 0.019$), between the respondents who perceived their workplace climates as 'poor' and those who perceived their workplace climates as 'excellent' ($z = 2.990$; $p = 0.003$), between those who perceived their workplace climates as 'satisfactory' and those who perceived their workplace climates as 'very satisfactory' ($z = 3.068$; $p = 0.002$), between those who perceived their workplace climates as 'satisfactory' and those who perceived their workplace climates as 'excellent' ($z = 5.068$; $p = 0.000$), and between those who perceived their workplace climates as 'very satisfactory' and those who perceived their workplace climates as 'excellent' ($z = 4.832$; $p = 0.000$).

No other pair-wise comparison of the means yielded a significant difference.

Table 9***The Posteriori (Mann-Whitney) Test Result for the Differences in the Levels of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents Classified according to their Perceptions of their Workplace Climate***

Compared Groups	z	p-value
Perception of Workplace Climate		
Poor vs. Satisfactory	1.846	0.065
Poor vs. Very Satisfactory	2.336*	0.019
Poor vs. Excellent	2.990**	0.003
Satisfactory vs. Very Satisfactory	3.068**	0.002
Satisfactory vs. Excellent	5.068***	0.000
Very Satisfactory vs. Excellent	4.832***	0.000

*p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001

The Relationship between the Level of Workplace Burnout and the Level of Job Satisfaction among the Respondents

The result of the Spearman's rho computation in Table 18 reveals a negative and very highly significant correlation between the respondents' of workplace burnout and their level of job satisfaction ($r = -0.291$; $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). This indicates that the job satisfaction among the respondents was a negative function of the level of workplace burn-out they experienced; that is, the respondents who experienced higher levels of workplace burnout have lower levels of job satisfaction, and vice versa.

The null hypothesis assuming a non- significant relationship in this regard was rejected.

These results may be explained by Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene theory. The respondents who had high burnout levels may have felt the absence of hygiene factors - organizational policy, supervision, their relationship with their boss, work conditions, salary, and relationships with peers - and motivating factors (e.g. challenging work, recognition for one's achievement, responsibility, opportunity to do something meaningful, involvement in decision making, sense of importance to an organization). As a result, they may not have developed a favorable perception of their organizational climate which led to low levels of job satisfaction. On the other hand, those who had low burnout levels may have experienced the presence of these hygiene and motivational factors which caused them to have higher of satisfaction with their jobs.

Moreover, the results of the present investigation confirm the assertion of Ogresta et al. (2020) which stipulated that researches consistently showed a negative correlation between burnout and job satisfaction. This means that as burnout levels increase, job satisfaction tends to decrease, and vice versa. Burnout can be a strong predictor of job satisfaction.

Table 18

The Spearman's-rho Test Results for the Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Workplace Burnout and Level of Job Satisfaction

Correlated Variables	N	r	p-value
Level of Workplace Burnout	151	-0.291***	0.000
Level of Job Satisfaction			

*** $p < 0.001$

Conclusions

Based on the results and findings, the researcher has drawn the following generalizations:

1. These results indicate that the respondents as an entire group the main cause of the burnout they experienced in the workplace was time pressure, which they described

as 'unrealistic', with regard to the submission of reports and other documents. This is probably because they had been required to submit these documents at such a limited time that they felt was too insufficient. Moreover, the respondents also experienced heavy burden with the frequency of changes in how the work they had to do and in the frequent changes in the format of the documents (i.e. syllabus, research format, etc.) that they had to accomplish. Probably they felt that before they could develop some higher level of expertise and proficiency in these tasks, the required methods for these tasks and the format for these documents were changed again. Further, the extra assignments, especially during the accreditations, aside from their regular working loads also contribute significantly to the workplace burnout experienced by the respondents and caused them to feel overwhelmed by their workloads, and they had to work long hours and had to take their work home.

2. These findings further indicate that most of the respondents believed that through praying they would be able to overcome the burnout they encountered in their workplaces. The respondents also preferred to ease the burdens that they experienced through spending quality time with their families and divert their attention from the rigors of their jobs by continuing to develop their knowledge and skills regarding their jobs, and by establishing harmonious relationships with their colleagues. Emotional self-regulation was also another way the respondents coped with workplace burnout because uncontrolled emotions was known to contribute to the feeling of burnout about something.
3. It is evident in the results that the respondents who had more favorable perceptions of their workplace climate experienced lower levels of workplace burnout. This indicates that workers who felt motivated and had sensed collaboration, efficiency, rapport and support from their colleagues and superiors in the workplace experienced less work-related chronic stress, emotional exhaustion, psychological distance or negativity, and low feelings of inefficacy.
4. The findings indicate that the job expectations of the respondents in general, as well as those who had a more favorable outlook of their workplace climate had been adequately met which accounts for their higher level of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction represents the extent to which optimism is aligned with actual rewards and advantages. It can be said therefore that, if workers have a favorable perception of the workplace, then they will likely experience fulfillment in their jobs.
5. The findings indicate that the respondents' perception of their workplace climate, or their feeling of well-being or lack of it in their workplace significantly influenced their feeling of work-related chronic stress, emotional exhaustion, psychological distance or negativity which is referred to as burnout. It was further revealed that the respondents who had a more positive perception of their workplace climate experienced lower levels of workplace burnout, and vice versa. Further, it can be said that the variations in the levels of workplace burnout experienced by the respondents may be directly attributed to the differences in their perceptions of their workplace climate and did not happen by chance.
6. Considering that the findings indicated that the respondents who had more favorable perceptions of their workplace environment had significantly higher levels of job

satisfaction may point out to the fact that the job expectations of these respondents, such as recognition, achievement, fair salary and favorable working conditions may have been adequately met which caused them to have higher levels of job satisfaction. Further, it can be said that the variations in the levels of job satisfaction among the respondents may be directly attributed to the differences in their perceptions of their workplace climate and did not happen by chance.

7. That there was a negative and highly significant correlation between the respondents' workplace burnout and job satisfaction indicates that there was an inverse, statistically valid relationship between these two factors where an increase in one variable is associated with a reliable, predictable decrease in another. It indicates that the two variables move in opposite directions, and this relationship is unlikely to have occurred by chance. These findings further indicate reducing the factors that contribute to the increase in workplace burnout would cause a predictable increase in job satisfaction.

Recommendations

Based on the results and the generalizations formulated, the researcher suggests the following courses of action:

1. The University officials may use the results of the investigation in retooling some existing policies concerning the welfare of its faculty and staff and, in the process, minimize, if not eliminate, workplace burnout among them. The University think-tanks may also find the information drawn from the findings of the important in crafting programs and activities that would further alleviate the working conditions of its employees.
2. The employees of the WVSUCC system who are the ultimate beneficiaries of the findings of this research may also learn tips on how to effectively cope with stress and burnout in the workplace. They may find the experiences of their fellow employees useful in making adjustments to their lifestyle, especially in terms coping with stress to promote a wholesome well-being for themselves.
3. The students, the parents, and the people in the community (the local government unit) may contribute to the well being of the employees by initiating programs and conducting activities together – like wellness programs - that would alleviate the working conditions in the various campuses of the University because if the living conditions of the employees are improved through the results of this study, then the other stakeholders may enjoy better services from the employees of the University.
4. The various campuses of the University may implement the stress management training program for WVSU Employees proposed by the researcher. The program may be strategically implemented on a long term basis and shall be monitored and evaluated periodically for continuous improvement.
5. Future researchers may embark on similar investigations, but with a wider scope, to further validate the results of this study.

6. The results of this study may be disseminated in classroom discussions and published in a reputable on-line platform.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors hereby declare that that they had obtained the informed consent of the respondents prior to data gathering and that the respondents were also informed that they had the freedom to withdraw their participation from the research at any time. The authors likewise ensured that the respondents' anonymity and all information pertaining to them, as well as their responses to the questionnaires, were kept in utmost secrecy at all times during and after the research. The researchers also safeguarded the well-being of the respondents and that the researchers had no conflict of interest with them in the conduct of the study. The researchers further declare that they avoided plagiarism at all times and they held no prejudices or biases against any person or any institution during the conduct of the study and they conducted the study solely for research purposes. The researchers further declare that they did not use AI in the discussion of the results, as well as in any part of the study, except in the definition of some terms.

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